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PROMISING STORIES FROM THE PILOT STUDIES

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Author

Lottie Provost, CNR-ILC

Contributors

Laura Himanen, CSC

Laurent Romary, INRIA

Thanasis Vergoulis, ATHENA RC

Andrea Mannocci, CNR-ISTI

Odile Hologne, OPERAS

Carol Delmazo, OPERAS

Fotis Mystakopoulos, OPERAS

Katri Rintamäki, UEF

Alina Irimia, UEFISCDI

Ioana Spanache, UEFISCDI

Ana Bošković, UNIBE

Jarno Hoekman, UU

Anestis Amanatidis, UU

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INTRODUCTION

This booklet outlines the implementation pathways and outcomes of nine Pilot studies conducted as part of the GraspOS project.

GraspOS, which stands for Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science, is a Horizon Europe Research & Innovation project supporting the reform of research assessment across the European Research Area. By developing services, tools, and infrastructure, the project aims to promote the transition to a Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) system that both aligns with and incentivises Open Science practices. Its main output is an EOSC-integrated, open, and federated infrastructure that aggregates resources for research assessment intended to support the implementation of emerging policy reforms.

The work of the Pilots

To drive this effort forward, nine Pilots co-designed, validated, and evaluated Open Science-aware indicators, tools, and services for RRA. These Pilots reflect three distinct assessment contexts:

- (1) Funding agencies and national stakeholders using infrastructure to support funding evaluation processes
- (2) Universities, including departments and research groups, interested in recruitment and assessment
- (3) Thematic disciplines that establish domain-specific assessment criteria aligned with disciplinary needs.

In this booklet, you will learn about the practical experimentation and collaborative design processes undertaken by the Pilots, including:

- Co-designing Open Science assessment protocols consistent with organisational and community policy frameworks.

- Co-creating researcher and organisational Openness Profile templates, including innovative indicators that represent different research artefacts and processes.
- Identifying infrastructure gaps and outline the necessary features for service development.
- Defining the characteristics of local or community requirements to support the development of fit-for-purpose services and tools.

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- [Recognising Open Science in a national CRIS](#)
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DEFINING COMPUTER SCIENCE PARTICULARITIES TO BETTER ASSESS RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The Computer Science Pilot, led by INRIA, ATHENA RC and UNIBO focuses on the academic and research community in computer science at large.

The goal is to analyse the scholarly specificities of this field and determine how its strong digital background can bring specific insights into Open Science and research assessment. By focusing on software, the Pilot also expected to provide insights for other communities where software plays an increasing role in the production, analysis, and dissemination of research data.

THE CHALLENGE

Computer Science has historically been a domain where openness was crucial, such as in the development of open-source software and the early online dissemination of research papers. However, traditional cross-domain research assessment practices often neglect essential characteristics of Computer Science research. Specifically, they fail to account for the importance of software as a research production that can be cited as a major career achievement. Another missed aspect is the importance of conferences as a major publication channel, sometimes surpassing journals in terms of quality in highly evolving fields. By focusing on software, the Pilot also expected to provide insights for other communities where software plays an increasing role in the production, analysis, and dissemination of research data.

OBJECTIVES

The primary aim was to study the particularities of the field by providing a landscape analysis of Open Science practices in Computer Science. This aim evolved to also include testing tools and services to allow research assessment processes to appropriately account for the

unique contributions of the Computer Science field.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The priority was to provide an exhaustive landscape analysis of Open Science practices in Computer Science and list all existing initiatives or infrastructures (e.g., Software Heritage, DBLP) that could serve as a basis for better coverage of the field from a research assessment viewpoint.

GraspOS partners developed and made available several resources (tools, data, services, etc.) for testing, including the OpenAIRE Graph, Opencitation Meta, BIP! Scholar, OpenAIRE MyResearchFolio, and SoftWARE-Hub (to extract software mentions from publications).

The Computer Science Pilot was involved in the fine-tuning and testing of these tools, with a particular effort made for identifying valuable components for the profiles of researchers in Computer Science.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The working group produced a comprehensive situation analysis in the form of a preprint report [1].

From this analysis, they identified specific experiments, such as providing a software usage dashboard for researchers and institutions. This dashboard is planned to be based upon the identification of software mentions in publications, with the perspective of eliciting both software reuse and dissemination within the community.

In addition, the team collected a number of fields important for inclusion in the profiles of computer scientists [2], which was provided as input to the academic profile tools and services offered by GraspOS partners.

The most considerable impact is the possibility to take into account the specifics of the Computer Science field at various levels of the project. The team hopes that Pilot institutions will be able to integrate these findings into their evaluation processes. The project successfully brought together diverse actors who could converge to make research assessment more responsible, which is considered a major outcome.

A major challenge remains between setting up proofs of concept and integrating them into stable research assessment infrastructures. It is necessary to see how research objects such as software and conferences can be fully incorporated into open information sources like Open Citations, OpenAIRE, or OpenAlex in the future.

Additionally, the Pilot study recognised that datasets are a major challenge, just as important as software or publications, and should probably be included in assessment processes.

References

- [1] <https://inria.hal.science/hal-04362464>
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Project Details

Project: GraspOS
Pilot: Computer Science
Lead contact: Laurent Romary
(laurent.romary@inria.fr)
Team: Thanasis Vergoulis, Silvio Peroni, Kumar Guha, Samuel Scalbert, Serafeim Chatzopoulos, Angelo Di Iorio
Funded under: Horizon Europe

RECOGNISING OPEN SCIENCE IN A NATIONAL CRIS

CSC – IT Center for Science is leading a piloting activity to recognise Open Science contributions in research assessment. Focusing on the national research information service Research.fi, this pilot explores how a national CRIS (Current Research Information System) can support more responsible and open-science aware practices in research information management.

Research.fi is a service offered by the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture that collects and disseminates information on research conducted in Finland. Currently, Research.fi contains information on the Finnish research system, publications by Finnish organisations, projects funded by public and private research funders, information on researchers operating in Finland and their research activities, and statistical information on the development of research resources and impact.

THE CHALLENGE

Open Science is a cornerstone of the evolving European research landscape, but integrating Open Science into research assessment practices remains complex. Research information management plays a crucial role in research assessment, yet existing assessment frameworks often overlook discipline-specific and sectoral differences, and tend to underrepresent the wide range of research activities that underpin science.

Responsible research assessment principles emphasise the importance of recognising diversity in research activities and practices, as well as prioritising qualitative assessment, and avoiding inappropriate use of metrics and indicators. Unfortunately, the documents guiding the reform on research assessment i.e. Agreement on reforming research assessment, DORA, Metric Tide, Leiden Manifesto) offer very little guidance on how to collect new types of information to support the assessment of diverse activities and practices, even less on how to

utilise new types of information in assessments.

Hence, a lot of development work needs to be done to define what these new types of activities and practices could be, how can information on these new types of activities and practices be collected in a reliable way, and finally, how can new types of information be stored and used in a meaningful way. To tackle this challenge, it is essential to find ways of highlighting competence and real effort, looking beyond standard metrics on open access publications, and without adding to researchers' administrative burden.

OBJECTIVES

This Pilot operated in the wider context of research information management, with the general objective to answer questions such as which aspects of Open Science should be shown on a national, organisational, sectoral or individual level and why. On a more specific level, the aims were to adopt and adapt the Openness Profile to the Research.fi

service, to enrich its metadata and support the improvement of indicators and metrics, and to co-shape APIs of the Open Research Assessment Infrastructure.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The Pilot team collaborated with the Research.fi Steering Group, which brings together representatives of Finnish research-performing, funding, and supporting organisations, by collecting their views and experiences regarding their needs for more Open Science-aware evaluation.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The concept of Openness Profile gained a lot of interest during the piloting, especially from researchers who are active in advancing Open Science and who would like to be credited for it. The question is how to highlight competence and real effort, looking beyond standard metrics on open access publications, and without adding to researchers' administrative burden.

On a theoretical level, the pilot contributed to widening researchers' and funders' understanding of Open Science as a merit, helping to distinguish between what constitutes true merit and what is merely compliance with external requirements. It also contributed to highlighting that simply opening an output should not be the focus; rather, it is essential to find ways to recognise and respect capabilities and competencies in Open Science.

The pilot further helped realise that recognition of Open Science practices is highly context-dependent, and reflects the level of maturity of Finnish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) in regard to Open Science. As a consequence, service providers like Research.fi need to continue to dig deeper into new data sources to be able to support a more

diverse idea of what should be included in an Openness profile.

On a technical level, the pilot tested the coverage and reliability of OpenCitations' data in reference to the publication data of a national-level research information system. While the integration of services like OpenCitations is still under discussion, the pilot has improved technical readiness and policy understanding. The Research.fi data model has been developed and enriched with relations, which will allow for more diverse information to be added to the Research.fi database in the future and inform broader European initiatives to include Open Science contributions in research assessment.

In summary, both piloted services have underlined the need to reflect on the purpose of collecting and disseminating research information, and on the potential outcomes and uses of such information in the context of Open Science and responsible research assessment.

Project details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: CSC, Finland

Lead contact: Laura Himanen
(laura.himanen@csc.fi)

Team: Iiris Ruoho, Maari Alanko

Funded under: Horizon Europe

FROM POLICY TO PRACTICE: ANALYSING CNR CAREER ADVANCEMENT CRITERIA IN LIGHT OF THE ARRA

The National Research Council of Italy (CNR) is the largest public research institution in Italy, and the only one under the Research Ministry performing multidisciplinary activities.

In 2022, CNR approved its "Relaunch Plan" which included a reform of the internal research assessment system. In November of the same year, CNR signed the CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA), committing to changing the assessment design for the career progressions of its researchers and technologists. The 2023 competitive calls for career progressions (the latest ones) involved over 2500 researchers and 500 technologists across different competition areas, with evaluation run autonomously by dedicated committees.

THE CHALLENGE

Italian Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) are generally assessed by the public agency ANVUR. This evaluation process, limited to scientific production, does not take into account the plurality of research products. Conversely, CNR autonomously evaluates its research staff members whenever a competitive call for career progression is open. Having signed the ARRA, a key challenge is to understand how the institution is complying with and fulfilling this commitment, particularly in light of the complexity and sensitive ramifications of the competitive call process.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the Pilot study were to analyse the evaluation criteria instantiated in the 2023 competitive calls, which strived to align with the ARRA. The pilot also aimed to map CNR's assessment design against the GraspOS infrastructure to understand how it could benefit the procedure (e.g., via the federated services, data, and tools). Finally, the team

planned to liaise with CNR direction to provide recommendations and engage with the scientific community to understand how the ongoing reform is perceived.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The approach was primarily conceptual and positioned downstream to the assessment design and evaluation phases, making direct testing of federated GraspOS tools and services unfeasible. The core work involved analysing the text of the four 2023 competitive calls for career advancement at CNR. This allowed the team to examine the narrative CV templates currently required by CNR and contextualise them against other available templates, such as the Royal Society's.

The analysis focused on the criteria produced within the 90 evaluation committees, across four career progression stages.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The team offered valuable feedback to both OpenAIRE and BIP! Finder teams to help refine and develop tools that support the integration of data-driven evidence into narrative CVs and dashboards. The pilot also helped the institution realise the value of assessment portfolios. For the first time, CNR shared the material assessed by the committees (CVs, research products, and scores) with all evaluands competing in the same call, which resembles a rudimentary version of the assessment portfolio concept designed in the project.

By analysing over 3800 individual criteria against the first four CoARA commitments, the pilot team was able to compile an extensive report for CNR's head of staff and recruitment offices. This report provides an in-depth self-reflection on how the reform has been interpreted by the committees and how the mandates have been fulfilled. The insights and actionable knowledge derived from this work are hoped to positively influence future competitive calls at CNR and contribute to redefining internal procedures for career progression, moving towards more inclusive, fair, and responsible research evaluation practices. The substantial data analysed and the findings obtained are currently being shaped into a journal article.

Career progression at CNR is a delicate process, which led to delays in selection procedures and, in some cases, legal disputes filed by evaluands. This experience suggests that an evaluation entirely based on a decentralised (yet open) infrastructure would be unfeasible for running mass assessment at CNR and similar RPOs. An institution such as CNR would rather focus on the institutional repository (i.e., IRIS for CNR) and explore in-house tools for evaluation campaigns. This creates a tension between centralised versus decentralised and open infrastructure for Responsible Research Assessment.

A possible solution would be to head towards a hybrid infrastructure where evaluation is supported primarily by an on-premise system (CRIS, institutional repository), complemented by off-premise decentralised data sources and services.

Project details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: CNR, Italy

Lead contact: Andrea Mannocci
(andrea.mannocci@cnr.it)

Team: Francesca Di Donato,
Fabrizio Pecoraro, Lottie Provost

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ADVANCING THE OPENNESS AND TRANSPARENCY OF SCIENCE BY EXPLORING NEW APPROACHES FOR ASSESSING OPEN SCIENCE AND UNDERSTANDING RESEARCH PRACTICES

INRAE, the National Institute for Research for Agriculture, Food and the Environment, is a French research performing organisation specialising in Agricultural Sciences with a long history of responsible research assessment, starting in 2010.

INRAE has an existing Open Science policy that covers openness and FAIRness of research outputs (publications, data, codes) and promotes participatory research. The institute is committed to promoting Responsible Research Assessment for researchers' career progression, taking into account Open Science practices, interdisciplinarity, and diverse activities.

THE CHALLENGE

INRAE's approach to Open Science is broad, encompassing engagement with different audiences and involving stakeholders throughout the research process, including participatory science and open innovation. Assessing the engagement and impact of Open Science is key for the institute and constitutes the focus of the Pilot. Additional challenges include issues related to data quality and the completeness of data aggregated from different sources, as well as the ability to accurately classify outputs according to different classifications.

OBJECTIVES

The Pilot aimed to understand researchers' and scientists' engagement with Open Science, taking into account the diversity of research outputs. The three guiding objectives were to monitor the uptake of the Open Science policy at INRAE; explore the

feasibility of using new indicators on interdisciplinarity, and support to policy or innovation; and help researchers create and enrich their openness profile and a narrative CV for an assessment portfolio.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

A collaborative approach with GraspOS technical partners was implemented, consistently highlighting the importance of data quality and supporting an open and reproducible methodology. The Pilot defined its strategy to include building an OpenAire gateway to aggregate data coming from different sources, such as publications, data, codes, grants, and patents.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The team developed a growing understanding of Data Aggregators like OpenAIRE and their crucial role in transforming how Open Science initiatives

are tracked and advanced. The Pilot study found that standardised indicators are still needed to effectively measure all dimensions of Open Science and its impacts. For example, a common definition of research products is necessary to measure openness rate consistently. The OpenAIRE CONNECT portal gateway and MONITOR services provided valuable insights, and the OpenAIRE Graph was identified as an essential tool for in-depth data analysis and experimenting with new indicators. The team also provided feedback on the OpenAIRE ecosystem, which revealed a number of data quality issues, allowing INRAE to rectify some of these with the data provider.

The findings provide crucial support to INRAE researchers to help them explain how they are involved in responsible research practices. The Pilot contributed to the development of a roadmap for building the OpenAIRE gateway and the involvement in GraspOS provided a great opportunity to interact with many actors, appreciating valuable insights regarding the diverse objectives of other institutions and the innovative services implemented by partners.

Overall, additional work will be required to generalise and institutionalise monitoring, particularly in areas such as data synchronisation between providers and the Data Aggregator, the widespread adoption of unique identifiers, and the ability to index research outputs on relevant thematics (like Fields of Science or Sustainable Development Goals). To help researchers create and enrich their profiles, there is a current need for a “Hub of data services” to facilitate the integration of usage services (citation, downloads, etc.) into INRAE’s own repositories.

The Pilot confirmed that an Open Science-aware research assessment system requires the best possible quality data, and OpenAIRE offers promising outlooks in this area.

Project details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: Agricultural and Veterinary
Sciences

Lead contact: Odile Hologne
(odile.hologne@inrae.fr)

Team: Alban Thomas, Naima
Cortes-Perez

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COMMUNITY VOICES IN RESEARCH ASSESSMENT: AN INSIDE LOOK AT THE SSH PILOT

The OPERAS Pilot is a thematic Pilot focusing on the challenges the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are facing with regards to research assessment, particularly concerning Open Access publishing.

OPERAS Research Infrastructure, with its expertise in scholarly communication and extensive network, is leading this activity focusing by listening to the community to understand their needs and priorities for research assessment reform.

THE CHALLENGE

SSH is widely recognised as an area requiring significant effort to adapt research assessment practices to its specific needs. Current assessment is measured disproportionately by quantitative indicators that primarily look at impact through citations derived from journal publications, often neglecting the necessary qualitative perspective. The biggest challenge is reaching a more diverse and qualitative-based solution for SSH, differentiating its value from STEM disciplines. Specific challenges include how to measure the impact of other important outputs to SSH, namely books, and how to embrace multilingualism when publications not in English may receive less attention, raising fundamental questions about assessing quality and impact.

OBJECTIVES

The objective was to discuss with the community the outputs and activities that should be valued in SSH research assessment, and how these can be aligned with open research infrastructures, and make assessment more Open-Science aware. Although, initially the pilot started from what data was available on research outputs such

as Open Access monographs, the Pilot expanded its focus to look at the broader activities which also deserve recognition.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

Relying on OPERAS' extensive reach and established partnerships across Europe, the approach was shaped as a co-creation effort, in line with the SCOPE principle "Evaluate with the evaluated."

This meant forming a Community of Practice and holding consultation and evaluation workshops aimed at identifying which outputs and activities should be valued in an Open Science-aware assessment. This participatory approach ensured a bi-directional flow of information and engagement with actors across many countries and types of stakeholders.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The co-creation process gave the SSH community a real voice and reinforced a strong sense of ownership. The pilot's key outcomes include a better understanding of the potential and limitations of narrative CVs in an evaluation setting with SSH nuances in mind, and a set of guidelines and recommendations on what to consider for

SSH research assessment. Finally, the pilot helped assess the use of some GraspOS services and tools in the domain context. For example, the test of the SSH Narrative CV took place within the BIP! Scholar platform. This exercise revealed how difficult it is to meaningfully include Open Science practices within that format.

Beyond the pilot's outputs, the feedback collected from these activities fed directly into the GraspOS SCOPE+i guidelines. This ensured that the community's voice was clearly reflected in the project's outputs.

Overall, through the Pilot, the team learned how to better work with the GraspOS infrastructure and provided grounded, community-informed feedback.

Maximising GraspOS' impact requires continued engagement with stakeholders to ensure guideline uptake and that data, tools, and services fulfill their purpose of making research assessment more open, transparent, and context-aware.

Project details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: Social Sciences and
Humanities

Lead contact: Fotis

Mystakopoulos

([fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-
eu.org](mailto:fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org))

Team: Carol Delmazo

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DEVELOPING A HYBRID INDICATOR MODEL FOR RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH ASSESSMENT AND OPEN SCIENCE EVALUATION

The University of Eastern Finland (UEF), a multidisciplinary university, led a pilot study to explore new methods for evaluating Open Science and supporting responsible research assessment.

UEF is committed to being a pioneer in Open Science and science communication in its Strategy 2030. UEF uses its institutional CRIS database and contributes publication data to the national service Research.fi.

THE CHALLENGE

While traditional indicators (publication and citation rates) serve the academic community, less-used indicators related to openness and popularisation are important for increasing the visibility and uptake of research findings across society. The latter indicators are needed to cover a broader range of activities and demonstrate the societal impact of research, ensuring scientific knowledge is used in everyday work where appropriate, such as professional practice, education, policy-making, public administration, and entrepreneurship.

OBJECTIVES

The UEF pilot aimed to improve the quality and societal impact of research by making science more open, accessible, and useful to stakeholders beyond academia. Specifically, the objectives were to analyse and test less-used publication and research activities indicators to determine whether they were fit for Open Science activities, and to explore new methods in knowledge management, impact assessment, and responsible research assessment.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

In the pilot study, the relevance of less-used data on publication and research activities (e.g., professional and popular publications, peer-reviewing, expert tasks, citizen science activities) were analysed to visualise openness and societal impact, and to promote the culture of open scholarship. Furthermore, UEF leading decision-makers were interviewed to gather their views on societal impact and Open Science activities.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The UEF Pilot successfully developed and piloted a new semi-quantitative hybrid indicator model for Open Science activities. This model is developed on evidence-based data and can be used to verify and make visible the societal interactions of a research organisation. The model highlights the diverse efforts researchers make toward achieving societal impact, based on institutional and national data. The semi-quantitative approach involved interpreting numerical values as star ratings.

The UEF pilot study successfully demonstrated the feasibility of this hybrid indicator.

It proved that it is possible to create an evidence-based multidimensional indicator model ("hybrid indicator") for the levels of societal interactions of Open Science. As these interactions are key to inducing societal impact, the hybrid indicator can be seen as an indirect evidence of the societal impact of Open Science.

This model sparked interest among university leadership and was praised for its value and potential for national research assessment, leading to its presentation to the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture. Findings indicate that including societal activities in research assessment is advantageous for promoting Open Science.

A major finding was that there are hardly any tools, services, or resources for managing scholarly activities other than publications. These are needed to recognise and reward merits in a wider range of academic activities, such as teaching, open education, open data, or supporting open scholarship culture. OpenAIRE Graph and OpenAIRE Explore were also tested in the pilot study. While the hybrid model is generally applicable, the structure and user interface of OpenAIRE Explore did not fully support the systematic comparison of research organisations needed for the model's development.

Finally, interviews with UEF leadership confirmed that Open Science is relevant across all branches of science, highlighting the ongoing need to cover different aspects of contribution, such as working with stakeholders as well as supporting open learning and citizen science.

Project details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: UEF, Finland

Lead contact: Katri Rintamäki
(katri.rintamaki@uef.fi)

Team: Heikki Laitinen, Anni
Tarkiainen

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DEVELOPING AND TESTING AN OPENNESS-AWARE RESEARCHER PROFILE IN ROMANIA

UEFISCDI is the main funder of competitive research in Romania, a key policy advisor, and a facilitator of dialogue within the research community.

UEFISCDI developed the National Open Science Strategic Framework, which mandates rethinking the current evaluation system to encompass a broader spectrum of research activities and outcomes, including Open Science practices.

THE CHALLENGE

The current national assessment system tends to value especially traditional outputs [1] such as publications and citations, while other significant contributions, such as databases, software, policy briefs, and contributions to public understanding of science are often overlooked. This Pilot sought to fill this gap by expanding the types of contributions to and activities of research that are made visible and recognised, allowing for a broader and more personalised representation of a researcher's impact, and directly aligning with CoARA's commitment to recognise diverse research outputs and activities.

OBJECTIVES

The Pilot focused on analysing, developing, and testing an enhanced Researcher Profile which features a dedicated Openness section by using the current platforms and Researcher profile (from the [BrainMap platform](#)). This redesigned profile aims to reimagine how researchers and their contributions are presented and recognised, offering a more inclusive and comprehensive depiction that captures the full breadth of their work and impact. The primary objective was to design and validate an Openness Researcher Profile that reflects a wider range of research contributions, aligns with CoARA

principles, and incorporates Open Science practices as well as elements inspired by narrative CVs.

In addition, the pilot also explored the feasibility of using tools and services (indicator toolboxes) in accordance with organisational policies and in alignment with CoARA's Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. Additionally, it conducted a preliminary analysis of the potential integration with the OpenAIRE Graph to assess interoperability and opportunities for enhanced data flows.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The new researcher profile prototype ([accessible here](#)) reimagines the existing profile layout, by building on already existing elements within the BrainMap platform while introducing new structures inspired by narrative CVs. Sections such as "Summary" and "Main Achievements" allow researchers to articulate the significance and impact of their work beyond metrics, showing a more contextualised representation of research careers.

Moreover, taking into account CoARA commitments and the OPUS Research Assessment Framework [2], the team aimed to bring to light a wider variety of contributions across categories such as research (e.g., projects, data, software, publications), education, leadership,

innovation, and engagement. The Openness profile section was designed as an additional layer within the reimagined Researcher profile, aggregating data from all categories of research outputs and contributions.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The Pilot successfully delivered a functional prototype of the enhanced Researcher Profile, including the new Openness section. This prototype represents a tangible step toward rethinking how researchers and their diverse contributions, including those related to Open Science, can be more visibly and fairly recognised within national research information systems.

A key achievement of the Pilot was the large-scale testing of the prototype through two national workshops involving more than 400 researchers from a wide range of disciplines. The profile was very well received, with participants acknowledging its relevance, clarity, and potential to reflect a broader spectrum of research practices. Feedback collected during these sessions provided valuable insights for refining the structure, content, and usability of the test profile.

These workshops also played an important role in stimulating national dialogue on the types of research outputs that are currently being recognised and rewarded at national level. The strong engagement demonstrated the increased interest for these topics existing within research communities, reinforcing the strategic relevance of the Pilot.

In addition to testing, the Pilot contributed to internal institutional reflection and helped shape UEFISCDI's CoARA Action Plan (2025–2028) [3], within which the GraspOS pilot is now embedded as a core activity driving assessment reform.

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Project details

Project: GraspOS
Pilot: UEFISCDI, Romania
Lead contacts: Alina Irimia
(alina.irimia@uefiscdi.ro), Ioana
Spanache
(ioana.spanache@uefiscdi.ro)
Team: Ioana Trif
Funded under: Horizon Europe

FOSTERING OPEN SCIENCE IN SERBIA THROUGH BADGES

The University of Belgrade – Faculty of Chemistry (UNIBE) is Piloting a new research assessment model grounded in the principles of Open Science and responsible metrics.

The Pilot integrates the institutional repository, Cherry, with a custom external application called Authors, Projects, Publications (APP). APP enhances monitoring by enabling data export, visualization, and the calculation of Open Access percentages, and functions as a narrative CV tool for capturing diverse research outputs. A distinctive feature is the badge-based reward model, which visually represents achievements in Green Open Access, departmental engagement, and participation in Open Science training.

THE CHALLENGE

In Serbia, the National Open Science Platform defined rules for depositing scientific results in institutional repositories. However, due to the absence of national monitoring, the assessment of researchers' adherence to Self-Archiving practices remains inconclusive. UNIBE, a pioneer in Open Science practices in Serbia, aims to improve recognition and reward systems at the department level to incentivise specific Open Science behaviors like self-archiving and engagement with training, shifting the focus beyond traditional metrics.

OBJECTIVES

The primary goal was to establish a new reward system at the University department level to improve Responsible Research Assessment. Specific objectives included developing a transparent in-departmental career assessment protocol, implementing a researcher Openness Profile within the repository environment, integrating OpenAIRE Research Graph data into dashboards, and refining metrics that support a more holistic and Open Science-aware assessment.

Key to this was the establishment of badges for researchers and departments applying Green Open Access, and for participating in Open Science and Responsible Research Assessment training.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The external application APP forms the foundation for the visual representation of the newly developed reward system. APP was introduced as a narrative CV tool, aligning with the SCOPE framework to support the recognition of diverse research outputs.

The system integrates external services like BIP!Ranker (for multidimensional impact metrics) and OpenCitations (for alternative citation data).

The badge-based reward system is central, with badges awarded for depositing publications (Green Open Access), promoting open practices, and active participation in Open Science events. The OpenAIRE Monitor Dashboard is also employed to provide institutional-level insights.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The establishment of the APP external application, which serves as both a narrative CV tool and the foundation for the visual reward system, is a key outcome.

The Pilot successfully implemented the badge-based reward system, which uses color-coding to indicate percentile rank and design to show the specific activity, providing a practical way to recognise and incentivise Open Science. The integration of external services like BIP!Ranker and OpenCitations enriches the evaluation framework, supporting continuous monitoring and transparency.

The most outstanding outcome is the establishment of a tangible and recognised reward system for Open Science practices, particularly Green Open Access, and relevant training participation. This signals a clear institutional commitment to Open Science and provides concrete incentives for researchers to adopt these practices. For the broader community in Serbia, the success of this Pilot could serve as a demonstrable model and a catalyst for other institutions to explore and implement similar efforts, reinforcing UNIBE's position as a pioneer in the field.

The initiative exemplifies how institutional collaboration between librarians, researchers, and technical staff can drive innovation in research assessment.

Participating in the GraspOS project provided a valuable framework to accelerate the improvement of Open Science practices at UNIBE. The Pilot directly supports GraspOS' mission by embedding Open Science practices into everyday academic evaluation and recognition, transforming research assessment systems to reflect openness, transparency, and societal impact.

Project Details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: UNIBE, Serbia

Lead contact: Ana Bošković

(anadj@chem.bg.ac.rs)

Team: Vladimir Otašević, Slađana

Savić Jovanović, Aleksa Savić,

Mihajlo Kulžić

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TESTING OPENAIRE DATA FOR THE EVALUATION OF TRANSDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

This Pilot focused on the Recognition and reward of Open Science practices in departmental research assessment at the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University (NL).

The Copernicus Institute conducts highly inter- and transdisciplinary research focused on the transition to sustainable societies with a prime focus on societal impact. The Pilot specifically investigated how transdisciplinary research, a staple Open Science practice at the department, is considered in the department's evaluation and the strength and weaknesses of OpenAIRE and CRIS data for the assessment of transdisciplinary research.

THE CHALLENGE

While Utrecht University holds a strategic Open Science Programme, translating it into everyday research practice is challenging. A key pillar of Open Science at the Copernicus Institute relates to societal impact creation and transdisciplinary research.

The challenge was to critically examine what data is, and can be, used for evaluating this pillar of Open Science at a departmental level as part of the periodic evaluation self-assessment for the six-yearly departmental evaluation. For this, the team defined a framework focusing on the evaluation of research processes, rather than solely outputs, because processes matter immensely in transdisciplinary research.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives were to document how Open Science is understood, operationalised, and evaluated in context at Utrecht University. The Pilot aimed to co-develop Open Science assessment protocols particularly at the level of the institute. It also sought to test the viability of indicators, tools, and services, particularly how they can inform Open Science monitoring, narrative writing

activities, and the assessment of societal impact.

IMPLEMENTATION APPROACH

The Pilot built on current Open Science monitoring activities and visions for novel forms of recognition put forward by the university's Open Science programme and the Dutch national strategy evaluation protocol, working across the institutional, research group, and individual levels. In the end, the team focused on how evaluation could benefit from OpenAIRE data about the Copernicus Institute. The data was complemented and compared with data from University Utrecht's local repository. Both datasets were assessed for completeness and relevance for evaluation purposes. The implementation involved a wide range of actors, including department leadership, research staff, and individuals responsible for research information infrastructures.

OUTCOMES AND IMPACT

The Pilot provided valuable real-life feedback to OpenAIRE researchers and engineers, as well as those managing the

local repository at Utrecht University, showcasing how they can adapt their tools and services to a changing research landscape. The Pilot helped sensitise the assumptions guiding the transition toward an Open Science-aware research assessment system. Most notably, the Pilot helped showcase how transdisciplinary research processes can be an important unit of evaluation for an Open Science-aware research assessment system while flagging that current research information providers and systems largely cannot be used or appropriated for its evaluation on departmental levels.

The University Utrecht Pilot provided recommendations and contributed to a more critical and reflective approach towards the use of data in evaluation. By focusing on processes rather than outputs, the Pilot study demonstrated an important pathway for recognising complex forms of research contributions that underpin sustainable research futures.

A key challenge identified was a significant lack of relevant research information in both Utrecht University's local repository and OpenAIRE regarding complex activities. This lack was especially pronounced when non-academic stakeholders are involved and activities are highly collaborative (e.g., 'co-designing a course for professionals' or 'co-producing knowledge').

This emphasises the importance of reflexive and intentional use of quantitative information for these purposes and a lack of effort to systematise monitoring of activities, relationships and events, rather than material outputs.

Furthermore, the findings raised new questions on how to inform the development of narrative descriptions of impact activities pursued by collectives within the institute, rather than individual researchers or project teams.

Project Details

Project: GraspOS

Pilot: University Utrecht,
Netherlands

Lead contact: Jarno Hoekman
(j.hoekman@uu.nl)

Team: Anestis Amanatidis, Arne
Hefting, Carolina Castaldi, Jeroen
Bosman

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INSIGHTS

1

Prioritise context-aware implementation and acknowledge complexity

Recognition of Open Science practices is highly dependent on the maturity level and specificities of the institution or scientific domain, as demonstrated by differences found even among CoARA signatories. Future efforts must recognise that context matters; what works for one institution or field of study may not suit another. Stakeholders must move beyond a one-size-fits-all approach and be sensitive to the considerable differences between institutions, even among those committed to the same reforms.

2

Widen the scope of what is valued

Moving beyond a narrow, quantitative focus on publications and citations requires addressing the core question of "What do we assess, and why?". To value Open Science in research assessment, stakeholders shift from rewarding mere compliance to recognising researchers' skills, capabilities and contributions. This means ensuring that Open Science practices are considered in the assessment process.

3

Leverage open information and open infrastructures

To effectively implement CoARA commitments and translate RRA principles into practice, stakeholders need reliable ways to expand what counts as valuable research outputs and contributions. The pilot studies highlighted the crucial role of open information and open infrastructures in achieving this shift. Infrastructure providers also require ongoing feedback to refine the tools and services needed to integrate diverse forms of evidence into assessment portfolios and openness profiles. Strengthening this ecosystem will enable a more complete and accurate representation of researchers' contributions.

4

Modernise digital systems and ensure data quality

A common challenge encountered across the Pilots is the tension between the rapidly evolving research landscape and existing institutional infrastructures, which often still operate in a 'traditional' setting with a focus on standard metrics. To properly consider the diversity of outputs and activities, significant investment is required. Pilots revealed a general lack of tools and resources for managing scholarly activities beyond publications. When assessing research processes, stakeholders must recognise the limited availability of relevant data, which highlights the need for improved data-collection mechanisms.

CONTACT US

graspos-pm@athenarc.gr

<https://graspos.eu/>

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